

Mesoscale full-field measurements for 3D-printed composites under delamination

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COMPOSITE MATERIALS

- High specific strength and stiffness
- Directional and localized reinforcement

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

- Design freedom and customization
- No need of massive post-processing

HOW CAN WE
PREDICT FAILURE?

PREDICT THE MECHANICAL
RESPONSE OF AM COMPOSITES

VISCOELASTIC
BEHAVIOR

DAMAGE
MODELING

MULTISCALE
CHARACTERIZATION

Images from solvay.com, collinsaerospace.com

Filament extrusion

Filament bonding mechanism

PREDICT THE MECHANICAL RESPONSE OF AM COMPOSITES

Influence of the printing strategy and parameters on the fracture behavior

Premature interface failure under loading

ARCHITECTURE-DRIVEN FAILURE

Multiscale failure of polymers and composites manufactured by FFF

MESOSCALE FRACTURE MECHANICS OF COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED BY FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION

a. Carbon fiber-reinforced PEEK specimens design and manufacturing

Miniature compact tension (CT) specimens

Specimens printing strategy to study the interlayer and intralayer failure of 3D-printed composites.

High-temperature extrusion

HEATED PLATFORM
AON3D M2 high-temperature printer.

b. Images acquisition

c. Images analysis

1. Cameras 2. microscope head 3. precision platform 4. CT specimen

ϵ = lagrangian strain

↓ Vic 3D

ϵ_{yy} [-]

MESOSCALE FRACTURE MECHANICS OF COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED BY FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION

Full-field measurements by DIC for miniature CT specimens with **alternate stacking**

Force-displacement response

INTERLAYER

CT specimens with 0°- 90° stacking

CT specimens with ±45° stacking

MESOSCALE FRACTURE MECHANICS OF COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED BY FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION

Full-field measurements by DIC for miniature CT specimens with **alternate stacking**

CT specimens with $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ stacking under INTERLAYER delamination

The measurements confidence enables the crack propagation tracking under loading

Scanning electron microscopy inspection

The layer stacking determines the strain concentration and damage propagation

MESOSCALE FRACTURE MECHANICS OF COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED BY FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION

Full-field measurements by DIC for miniature CT specimens with **alternate stacking**

CT specimens with $\pm 45^\circ$ stacking under INTERLAYER delamination

Crack transfer to the adjacent interface

Scanning electron microscopy inspection

The $\pm 45^\circ$ alternate stacking results in the crack transfer to an adjacent interface

MESOSCALE FRACTURE MECHANICS OF COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED BY FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION

Full-field measurements by DIC for miniature CT specimens with **alternate stacking**

CT specimens with $\pm 45^\circ$ stacking under INTRALAYER delamination

Force-displacement response

I. Load = 2561 N II. Load = 2434 N III. Load = 2412 N

Strain field evolution

DIC RAW IMAGE AFTER FAILURE

The $\pm 45^\circ$ alternate stacking results in the energy intensive zig-zag crack propagation

MESOSCALE FRACTURE MECHANICS OF COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED BY FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION

Full-field measurements by DIC for miniature CT specimens with **alternate stacking**

CT specimens with $\pm 45^\circ$ stacking under INTRALAYER delamination

Force-displacement response

Scanning electron microscopy inspection

The fibers breakage results in the peak load and fracture energy increase

MESOSCALE FRACTURE MECHANICS OF COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED BY FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION

X-ray tomography inspection and segmentation with OpenFiberSeg [2]

Fibers alignment along the deposition direction

Porosity concentration at the layers' interface

Interface delamination as primary failure mechanism for composites manufactured by FFF

Fracture toughness doubling when the failure involves the filament breakage

Outcomes

- The layer stacking and printing strategy determine the damage nucleation and propagation under loading
- The embedment of carbon fibers enhances the mechanical properties in the filaments' direction
- The fiber reinforcement does not contribute to the interface strengthening, worsened by interfilament porosity

Multiscale characterization of the fracture mechanics of additively manufactured short fiber-reinforced composites, A. Lingua, F. Sosa-Rey, S. Pautard, D. Therriault, M. Lévesque, [Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 2023](#).

Future research directions

Influence of the temperature on the fracture behavior of composites manufactured by FFF

Volumetric fracture mechanics of 3D-printed composites

Thank you for your attention

